

NOTES

TABLE 2—MORPHOLINO/DIETHYLAMINO-DITHIOCARBAMYL-METHYL 3-(ARYL-SUBSTITUTED)-QUINAZOLIN-4-ONES

Sl. No.	R	R'	m.p.	Mol. formula	Nitrogen Analysed	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	-Morpholino	-phenyl	121-22°	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.59%	10.43%
2.	-Morpholino	-p-methyl phenyl	111°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.22%	10.51%
3.	-Morpholino	-p-methoxy phenyl	128-29°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	9.83%	10.03%
4.	-Morpholino	-methyl benzimidazolyl	82-83°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	15.52%	15.26%
5.	-Morpholino	-ethyl benzimidazolyl	187-88°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	15.05%	15.42%
6.	-Diethylamino	-phenyl	143-44°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS ₂	10.96%	11.16%
7.	-Diethylamino	-p-methyl phenyl	94-95°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS ₂	10.58%	10.39%
8.	-Diethylamino	-p-methoxy phenyl	132-33°	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	10.17%	10.47%
9.	-Diethylamino	-methyl benzimidazolyl	114-15°	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₄ OS ₂	16.01%	16.25%
10.	-Diethylamino	-ethyl benzimidazolyl	144-45°	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₄ OS ₂	15.52%	15.71%

Note: All the melting points are uncorrected. Yield ranged from 55-60%.

mean survival time (M.S.T.) were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Survival Percentage} = \frac{\text{Survival number of animals}}{\text{Initial number of animals}} \times 100$$

$$\text{M.S.T.} = \frac{\text{Summation of time taken for each animal to die} + \text{Summation of survival time of animals not dying}}{\text{Number of animals dying} + \text{Number of animals surviving}}$$

Results

The compounds 4 and 9 were found to possess 10% antiviral activity (net protection) while rest were found inactive.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of Novel Insecticides. Part-IV: Synthesis of S-(acetyl-N-substituted phenyl amine)-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazoles

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TWENTY substituted thiadiazoles were synthesized as possible insecticides by the condensation of chloroacetyl amine with sodium salt of various thiadiazoles.

TABLE

Sl. No.	R ¹	R ²	m.p. °C	Yield	Molecular formula	%Nitrogen		Mean K.D. (Knock down) time	
						Found	Calcd.	(hrs) % Concentration	
								0.5%	0.1%
1.	H	H	161-64	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS ₂	16.01	16.18	25.0	30.5
2.	H	2-CH ₃	180	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	15.40	15.55	19.5	22.0
3.	H	4-CH ₃	166-68	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	15.43	15.55	16.0	18.0
4.	H	2-Cl	185	67	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.61	14.89	13.0	15.5
5.	H	3-Cl	161	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.70	14.89	13.5	15.0
6.	2-CH ₃	H	180	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	15.30	15.55	17.0	20.5
7.	2-CH ₃	2-Cl	178	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.10	14.35	9.0	10.5
8.	3-CH ₃	H	200	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	15.36	15.55	15.5	17.0
9.	4-CH ₃	H	155	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS ₂	15.39	15.55	14.5	18.0
10.	4-CH ₃	2-Cl	178	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	14.19	14.35	11.5	13.0
11.	2-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	186-88	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	14.61	14.50	22.0	26.5
12.	2-OCH ₃	3-CH ₃	135	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	14.59	14.50	19.5	23.0
13.	2-OCH ₃	3-Cl	145-47	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	13.87	13.79	10.0	12.0
14.	4-OCH ₃	H	168-70	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	16.17	15.05	19.0	20.5
15.	3-Cl	H	166	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.58	14.89	14.5	16.0
16.	3-Cl	2-CH ₃	117-19	67	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.28	14.35	12.5	14.5
17.	4-Cl	2-CH ₃	212-14	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.27	14.35	14.5	16.0
18.	4-Cl	3-CH ₃	260	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl	14.31	14.35	10.0	11.5
19.	4-Cl	3-Cl	160	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl ₂	14.30	13.14	8.0	9.5
20.	4-Cl	4-Cl	165-67	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS ₂ Cl ₂	13.29	13.14	9.5	11.0

Thiadiazoles are known for their fungicidal¹⁻² and insecticidal³⁻⁵ properties. Various hydroxides have been reported as antibacterial⁶. 2-Mercapto-5-arylamino thiadiazoles were shown to be pesticidal and fungicidal agents by Giri *et al*⁷ and Sengupta *et al*⁸. Keeping these facts in view the synthesis of some substituted thiadiazoles by the condensation of chloroacetyl amine with sodium salt of 2-mercapto-5-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazoles was undertaken. The effects of various substituents on their insecticidal activities were studied.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Chloroacetyl phenyl amines were synthesized by the known methods and 2-mercapto-5-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazoles have been synthesized by reported methods⁹⁻¹⁰.

Synthesis of S-(acetyl-N-substituted phenyl amine)-N-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazoles :

2-Mercapto-5-arylamino-1,3,4 thiadiazole (0.01 mol) and sodium hydroxide (0.01 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 15 minutes on water bath. A solution of chloroacetyl amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added to this solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs on water bath. The resultant solution was cooled and poured into ice cold water and kept overnight. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and

recrystallised from ethanol. The melting points and analytical data are recorded in the Table.

Insecticidal Activity :

Compounds were evaluated for their insecticidal activity on adult male and female cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*) as the test insect following the method of Joshi *et al*¹¹. All the experiments were carried out in duplicate and the results are given in the Table. Compound No. 19 has been found to be most potent for its insecticidal activity.

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